

APPENDIX

A. SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIALS

A.1 *Model alternatives*

The Multispecies Coalescent model predicts a precise relationship among the quartet frequencies associated with each four taxon-subset. Thus, the weights associated with these quartets are statistically dependent. This issue could be addressed using only the best-scoring quartet among the three alternatives, building the correlation between the quartet frequencies directly into the weight function, or both.

The first alternative selects the maximum Associated Bayes Factor of the three quartet topologies rather than averaging over all three quartet topologies.

$$BF_{max} = \max_{q_1, q_2, q_3} \left(\frac{\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^1 p^{k_i} (1-p)^{n-k_i} dp}{\int_0^1 p^{k_i} (1-p)^{n-k_i} dp} \right).$$

Alternatively, under the full tree Multispecies Coalescent model, the quartet that matches the species tree should occur with a probability greater than $\frac{1}{3}$ with the two alternative topologies occurring with equal probability. We can consider the full Bayes Factor BF_{full} comparing H_1 : that the observed quartet frequencies were drawn from the multispecies coalescent model to H_2 that the quartets were drawn from an arbitrary multinomial distribution.

If we denote the probability simplex as $\Delta = \{(x_1, x_2, x_3) | x_i \geq 0, x_1 + x_2 + x_3 = 1\}$, then the Bayes Factor of $H_1 : H_2$ is given by

$$BF_{full} = \frac{\int_0^1 \left(\frac{p}{3}\right)^{b+c} \left(1 - \frac{2p}{3}\right)^a + \left(\frac{p}{3}\right)^{a+c} \left(1 - \frac{2p}{3}\right)^b + \left(\frac{p}{3}\right)^{a+b} \left(1 - \frac{2p}{3}\right)^c dp}{\int_{\Delta} 6x_1^a x_2^b x_3^c dx_i}.$$

Finally, we could choose the Bayes Factor associated with the hypothesis H_1 that an individual quartet is dominant under the full multispecies coalescent model vs. H_2 , that the quartets were drawn from an arbitrary multinomial distribution. If the quartet under consideration appears on a gene trees, and the alternative topologies are observed on b and

c gene trees, the Bayes Factor is

$$BF_{full_{q_i}} = \frac{\int_0^1 (\frac{p}{3})^{b+c} (1 - \frac{2p}{3})^a \frac{1}{9} dp}{\int_{\Delta} 6x_1^a x_2^b x_3^c, dx_i}$$

We select the highest associated $BF_{full_{q_i}}$ among the three quartet topologies in this alternative model.

Figure A1. Regions shaded red indicate that the associated score model would reject a concordance factor at a particular Bayes Factor cutoff. Regions shaded in teal indicate concordance factors that the associated model and threshold would accept. We plot concordance factors as percentages (a, b, c) given a set of 50 gene trees.

Figure A1 shows which sets of concordance factors would meet BF thresholds for the *PickMe* score and these three alternative models. We see that the BF_{full} and $BF_{full_{q_i}}$ include samples with limited signal while rejecting samples with relatively strong signal toward a particular quartet, given a slight imbalance in the frequencies of the non-dominant quartets. While the full coalescent model may better address issues of potential hybridization, the *PickMe* classification is better targeted toward filtering samples with limited signal. While quartets associated with short internal branches would

be penalized under the coalescent weight, this is likely to have a negligible impact on the sample selection, as short-edge quartets would represent only a small fraction of the quartets on which an individual sample appears.

A.2 Proof of Coalescent Weight Formula

The properties of the coalescent weight functions are specific application results on incomplete β function. Dutka provides a beautiful history of this function whose study predates the development of calculus Dutka (1981). The incomplete β function is defined by

$$B_x(a, b) = \int_0^x t^{a-1}(1-t)^{b-1} dt.$$

The regularized incomplete β function is defined by $I_x(a, b) = \frac{B_x(a, b)}{B(a, b)}$ where $B(a, b) = B_1(a, b)$ is the traditional β function $B(a, b)$.

In this context, we have

$$\begin{aligned} w(n, k) &= \frac{B(k+1, n-k+1) - B_{\frac{1}{3}}(k+1, n-k+1)}{B(k+1, n-k+1)} \\ &= 1 - I_{\frac{1}{3}}(k+1, n-k+1) \\ &= I_{\frac{2}{3}}(n-k+1, k+1). \end{aligned} \tag{A.1}$$

We note that the symmetry $I_x(a, b) = 1 - I_{1-x}(b, a)$ follows from the change of coordinates $T = (1-t)$ in the integrals defining $I_x(a, b)$.

Now consider $T : \mathbb{Z}_{n,k}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_{A,B}^2$ given by $T(n, k) = (n-k+1, k+1)$, so that $w(n, k) = I_{\frac{2}{3}}(t(n, k))$. Moreover the transformation is invertible, with $T^{-1}(A, B) = (A+B-2, B-1)$.

We can thus study the coalescent weight either in the space of $\mathbb{Z}_{n,k}^2$ or in $\mathbb{Z}_{A,B}^2$.

Figure A2. **Transformation** $T : \mathbb{Z}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}^2$ given by $T(n, k) = (n - k + 1, k + 1)$. The blue (resp. red and grey) dots in the right hand coordinate system, represent the image of the blue (resp. red and grey) under the linear transformaton which maps the space of scores $w(n, k)$ to the set of values of the regularized incomplete β -function $I_{\frac{2}{3}}(T(n, k))$

THEOREM A.1 The coalescent weight function $w(n, k)$ has the following properties:

1. For a fixed n if $k_1 > k_2$, then $w(n, k_1) > w(n, k_2)$.
2. For a fixed k if $n_1 > n_2$, then $w(n_1, k) < w(n_2, k)$.
3.
$$\begin{cases} w(n, k) < 0.5 & \text{if } \frac{k}{n} < \frac{1}{3}. \\ w(n, k) > 0.5 & \text{if } \frac{k}{n} > \frac{1}{3}. \end{cases}$$
4.
$$\lim_{\lambda \rightarrow \infty} w(\lambda n, \lambda k) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \frac{k}{n} < \frac{1}{3}. \\ 0.5, & \text{if } \frac{k}{n} = \frac{1}{3}. \\ 1 & \text{if } \frac{k}{n} > \frac{1}{3}. \end{cases}$$

Proof.

Property 1: Fix a value n and let $k_1 > k_2$ so that $k_1 = k_2 + m$ for some positive integer m . Then

$$\begin{aligned} T(n, k_1) &= (n - k_1 + 1, k_1 + 1) \\ &= (n - k_2 - m + 1, k_2 + m + 1) \\ &= T(n, k_2) + (-m, m). \end{aligned}$$

Since $I_x(A, B)$ is monotonically decreasing in A and increasing in B it follows that

$$I_{\frac{2}{3}}(T(n, k_1)) > I_{\frac{2}{3}}(T(n, k_2)).$$

Therefore $w(n, k_1) > w(n, k_2)$.

Property 2: Now fix a value of k and let $n_1 > n_2$ so that $n_1 = n_2 + m$ for some positive integer m . Then

$$\begin{aligned} T(n_1, k) &= (n_1 - k + 1, k + 1) \\ &= (n_2 + m - k + 1, k + 1) \\ &= T(n_2, k) + (m, 0). \end{aligned}$$

Since $I_x(A, B)$ is monotonically decreasing in A it follows that

$$I_{\frac{2}{3}}(T(n_1, k)) < I_{\frac{2}{3}}(T(n_2, k)).$$

Therefore $w(n, k_1) > w(n, k_2)$.

Property 3: Since $I_x(a, b)$ is the cumulative distribution function of the β -distribution, asking if $I_{\frac{2}{3}}(n - k + 1, k + 1) > 0.5$ is equivalent to asking if the median of the β distribution $B(n - k + 1, k + 1)$ is greater than or less than $\frac{2}{3}$. Here the median being less than $\frac{2}{3}$ would imply that $w(n, k) > 0.5$; if the median was greater than $\frac{2}{3}$ it follows that $w(n, k) < 0.5$

The β -distribution has known mean $\mu = \frac{a}{a+b}$ and mode $m = \frac{a-1}{a+b-2}$. The median of the β -distribution is bounded by its mean and mode (Kerman, 2011; Groeneveld and

Meeden, 1977). Therefore the median of $\beta(x, n - k + 1, k + 1)$, is bounded between $\frac{n-k+1}{n+2}$ and $\frac{n-k}{n}$. Now assume $n = 3k + M$ for some integer M . Then we have mean $= \frac{2k+M}{3k+M}$. From the quotient rule, the mean is an increasing function in M from which it follows that the median is greater than $\frac{2}{3}$ if $M > 0$ and less than $\frac{2}{3}$ if $M < 0$. Moreover, the mean is $\frac{2}{3}$ when $M = 0$.

For the mode, we have $m = \frac{2k+M+1}{3k+M+2}$, which by the quotient rule is also an increasing function in M . When $M = 1$ is 1 we have $m = \frac{2k+1+1}{3k+1+2} = \frac{2(k+1)}{3(k+1)} = \frac{2}{3}$. When $M = -1$ we have $m = \frac{2k-1+1}{3k-1+2} = \frac{2k}{3k+1} < \frac{2}{3}$. Since the median is bounded between the mean and the mode, it follows that $w(n, k) = \begin{cases} < 0.5 & \text{if } \frac{k}{n} < \frac{1}{3}. \\ > 0.5 & \text{if } \frac{k}{n} > \frac{1}{3}. \end{cases}$

Property 4: Now consider $W(\lambda n, \lambda k)$ for non-negative integer values n, K and $\lambda > 1$. We have $W(\lambda, \lambda k) = I_{\frac{2}{3}}(\lambda(n - k) + 1, \lambda k + 1)$. Recall that $I(a, b)$ is the cumulative distribution function of the β -distribution $\beta(a, b)$ which has mean $\mu[X] = \frac{a}{a+b}$.

Substituting $a = \lambda(n - k) + 1$ and $b = \lambda k + 1$ yields

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{\lambda \rightarrow \infty} \mu[x] &= \lim_{\lambda \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\lambda(n - k) + 1}{\lambda(n - k) + 1 + \lambda k + 1} \\ &= \lim_{\lambda \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\lambda(n - k) + 1}{\lambda n + 2} \\ &= \frac{n - k}{n}. \end{aligned}$$

The variance of the β -distribution $\beta(a, b)$ is given by $Var[X] = \frac{ab}{(a+b)^2(a+b+1)}$.

Substituting $a = \lambda(n - k) + 1$ and $b = \lambda k + 1$ yields

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{\lambda \rightarrow \infty} Var[X] &= \lim_{\lambda \rightarrow \infty} \frac{(\lambda(n - k) + 1)(\lambda k + 1)}{(\lambda(n - k) + 1 + \lambda k + 1)^2(\lambda(n - k) + 1 + \lambda k + 1 + 1)} \\ &= \lim_{\lambda \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\lambda^2 k(n - k) + \lambda n + 1}{(\lambda n + 2)^2(\lambda n + 3)} \\ &= \lim_{\lambda \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\lambda^2 k(n - k) + \lambda n + 1}{\lambda^3 n^3 + 7\lambda^2 n^2 + 16\lambda n + 12} = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, as λ increases, the probability density function is increasingly concentrated around the mean, $\frac{n-k}{n}$. Thus $I_{\frac{2}{3}}(\lambda(n-k)+1, \lambda k+1)$ approaches zero if $\frac{n-k}{n} > \frac{2}{3}$, approaches one if $\frac{n-k}{n} < \frac{2}{3}$ and approaches 0.5 if $\frac{n-k}{n} = \frac{2}{3}$. Which completes the proof that

$$\lim_{\lambda \rightarrow \infty} w(\lambda n, \lambda k) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \frac{k}{n} < \frac{1}{3}. \\ 0.5 & \text{if } \frac{k}{n} = \frac{1}{3}. \\ 1 & \text{if } \frac{k}{n} > \frac{1}{3}. \end{cases} \quad \square$$

A.3 Relationship between Bayes Factors and κ values

THEOREM A.2 Let κ be a real number greater than 1 and $BF(q)$ be the Bayes Factor in favor of the hypothesis that q is a dominant quartet. $BF(q)$ is either greater than κ or less than $\frac{1}{\kappa}$ if and only if, the reliability score $R(q) > \frac{k-1}{k+1}$.

Proof. Assume $BF(q) > \kappa$. Then since $BF(q) = \frac{w(q)}{1-w(q)}$ it follows that $\frac{w(q)}{1-w(q)} > \kappa$. Isolating $w(q)$ yields $w(q) > \frac{\kappa}{1+\kappa}$.

Now since $\kappa > 1$ also get that $w(q) > \frac{1}{2}$ therefore

$$\begin{aligned} R(q) &= 2|w(q) - \frac{1}{2}| \\ &= 2(w(q) - \frac{1}{2}) \\ &\geq 2(\frac{\kappa}{1+\kappa} - \frac{1}{2}) \\ &= 2\frac{2\kappa - (1+\kappa)}{2(1+\kappa)} \\ &= \frac{k-1}{k+1}. \end{aligned}$$

which means that $R(q) = 2w(q) - 1$ which implies $R(q) > \frac{2\kappa}{1+\kappa} - 1$. The claim follows from combining terms.

Now assume $BF(q) < \frac{1}{\kappa}$. Then since $BF(q) = \frac{w(q)}{1-w(q)}$ it follows that $\frac{w(q)}{1-w(q)} < \frac{1}{\kappa}$. Isolating $w(q)$ yields $w(q) < \frac{1}{1+\kappa}$.

Now since $\kappa > 1$ also get that $w(q) < \frac{1}{2}$ therefore

$$\begin{aligned} R(q) &= 2|w(q) - \frac{1}{2}| \\ &= 1 - 2w(q) \\ &\geq 1 - 2\frac{1}{1+\kappa} \\ &= \frac{1+\kappa-2}{1+\kappa} \\ &= \frac{k-1}{k+1}. \end{aligned}$$

The proof that $R(q) < \frac{k-1}{k+1}$ implies that $BF(q)$ is between κ and $\frac{1}{\kappa}$ follows the same line of reasoning. □

A.4 *Kappa Threshold*

In Bayesian statistics, $\{3,10,30,100\}$ are commonly used as the standard thresholds to evaluate the strength of support for hypothesis tests. We designed a brief simulation study to determine a standard threshold in the context of sample selection. A strong cutoff for kappa should include samples appropriate for a species tree analysis and reject unsupported samples. Absent a rigorous model for what constitutes a bad sample, we simulate the ability of *PickMe* to identify samples arbitrarily placed on gene trees.

Species trees with 10, 50, and 100 leaves were generated using SimPhy-1.0.2 (Mallo et al., 2016). We simulated collections of 10, 50, and 100 binary gene trees for each species tree under the multispecies coalescent model, assuming a speciation rate of 0.0001 (speciation events per generation), an effective population size of 10,000, and a single individual per species.

We assigned each sample a fixed probability of removal from a uniform distribution on the interval $[0, 1 - \frac{6}{m}]$, where m is the number of total samples. Samples were trimmed from each gene tree according to their probability of removal.

We selected a fixed number of samples (1, 2, or 5) for each species tree as *bad samples*. These bad samples were trimmed from all gene trees on which they appeared and reinserted along randomly selected edges. We tested the sensitivity and specificity of *PickMe* in correctly classifying the samples across the twenty-seven data sets. Cutoff values for the Bayes Factor threshold ranged from 1.5 to 30 in increments of 0.5. As it is unclear whether type I or type II error would be preferable, we computed a measure introduced in Serrano (2021) to balance the importance of avoiding false negatives and false positives: $F_\beta = \frac{(1 + \beta^2)PR}{\beta^2P + R}$ where P precision and R is the recall. We compute this measure for $\beta = 0.5, 1, 1.5$.

Based on the simulation results in Figure A3, we recommend the threshold value of $\kappa = 10$ as it is the highest performing threshold among the traditional thresholds 3, 10, 30, 100.

a)

b)

Figure A3. **Comparison of associated Bayes-Factor cutoff values for sample selection.** Twenty-seven data combinations of 10, 50, or 100 sample species trees, with 10, 50, or 100 sampled gene trees and 1, 3, or 5 errant samples were used to test *PickMe*'s ability to identify randomly placed samples. a) Sensitivity and Specificity of the *PickMe* recommendation of good and errant samples as a function of the associated Bayes-Factor threshold. b) F_{β} scores for the *PickMe* recommendation of good and errant samples as a function of the associated Bayes-Factor threshold. In both figures, samples are included if and only if the associated Bayes Factor exceeds the threshold on the x-axis.

A.5 Milkweed sample information

Table A1. Milkweed sample voucher information, sequencing and assembly success, and gene occupancy. Gene recovery indicates the presence of a targeted gene in the assembly. It includes partial sequences, while gene occupancy values indicate the number of genes for which a sequence was assembled that was long enough for inclusion in the final sequence matrix. **Sample was included by Boutte et al. (2019). † Values calculated for the 768 gene set.

Species	Voucher Herbarium	Number of reads	Number of reads mapped	Total assembled sequence length bp.†	Gene Recovery 768 Gene Set	Gene Recovery 703 Gene Set including partial sequences	Gene Occupancy 703 Gene Set partial sequences removed.
<i>A. aff. glaucescens</i>	Fishbein 3671 [ARIZ]	903 180	5,595 (0.62%)	39 301	104	97	6
<i>A. aff. pringlei*</i>	Carranza 2538 [OKLA]	1,434,236	120,559 (8.41%)	884,364	602	562	349
<i>A. aff. puberula*</i>	Fishbein 6961 [OKLA]	949,080	455,035 (47.94%)	2,057,560	768	703	693
<i>A. aff. standleyi*</i>	Reina 98-379 [ARIZ]	3,154,034	1,565,575 (49.63%)	2,774,923	768	703	703
<i>A. albicans*</i>	Fishbein 3146 [WS]	2,069,520	542,378 (26.21%)	2,455,612	763	701	684
<i>A. alticola</i>	Fishbein 6938 [OKLA]	1 429 862	19,610 (1.37%)	108 655	97	92	27
<i>A. amplexicaulis*</i>	Fishbein 7501 [OKLA]	2,467,326	1,344,128 (54.48%)	3,062,324	765	703	703
<i>A. angustifolia</i>	Reina 2004-1315 [ARIZ]	410,990	55,466 (13.50%)	759,191	334	316	184
<i>A. arenaria*</i>	Correll and Johnston 20327 [LL]	3,074,388	1,444,226 (46.98%)	2,825,192	766	703	703
<i>A. atroviolacea*</i>	Fishbein 3612 [ARIZ]	2,561,498	339,544 (13.26%)	1,455,080	711	655	481
<i>A. californica</i>	Lynch 10779 [OKLA]	167,298	38,839 (23.22%)	540	2	2	0
<i>A. circinalis</i>	Webster 17186 [DAV]	127,924	1,241 (0.97%)	943	4	4	0
<i>A. contrayerba</i>	Fishbein 2493 [ARIZ]	350,680	112,832 (32.18%)	33,644	107	103	18
<i>A. cutleri*</i>	Lynch 1890 [OKLA]	2,796,316	1,426,140 (51.00%)	2,677,037	768	703	703
<i>A. curtisii*</i>	Fishbein 2421 [ARIZ]	2,197,990	771,419 (35.10%)	2,531,773	766	702	699
<i>A. cutleri</i>	Fishbein 6511 [OKLA]	419,710	66,320 (15.80%)	853,457	400	370	228
<i>A. elata*</i>	Worchester 6943 [OKLA]	4,331,854	1,949,560 (45.01%)	2,676,548	768	703	703
<i>A. emoryi*</i>	Worcester 114 [OKLA]	5,517,972	2,684,095 (48.64%)	2,577,807	768	703	703
<i>A. engelmanniana</i>	Fishbein 7518 [OKLA]	933 098	3, 932 (0.42%)	29 019	23	20	7
<i>A. erosa*</i>	Hufford 3593 [OKLA]	1,800,230	557,657 (30.98%)	2,313,443	763	701	700
<i>A. euphorbifolia*</i>	Fishbein 6965 [OKLA]	1,482,400	692,019 (46.68%)	2,292,723	768	703	701
<i>A. feayi</i>	Fishbein 5586 [OKLA]	832,168	223,356 (26.84%)	680,051	588	552	251
<i>A. fourmieri</i>	Lynch 1655 [OKLA]	1,166,100	561,517 (48.15%)	479,971	581	542	268
<i>A. hirtella*</i>	Fishbein 7502 [OKLA]	3,447,994	1,798,229 (52.15%)	3,193,799	768	703	703
<i>A. jaliscana</i>	Fishbein 6959 [OKLA]	1,712,208	6,540 (0.38%)	37,053	60	57	10
<i>A. latifolia</i>	Fishbein 7524 [OKLA]	1 237 140	25,323 (2.05%)	212 885	132	122	54
<i>A. linaria*</i>	Fishbein 6915 [OKLA]	947,844	507,021 (53.49%)	2,180,540	766	703	699
<i>A. longifolia*</i>	Fishbein 2414 [ARIZ]	1,333,836	426,300 (31.96%)	2,081,983	760	701	672
<i>A. lynchiana</i>	Venable and Becerra s.n. [ARIZ]	745 692	14,702 (1.97%)	122 469	186	173	20
<i>A. macroura</i>	Gentry 6448 [ARIZ]	222 228	500 (0.23%)	4,671	4	0	0
<i>A. mexicana*</i>	Fishbein 3009 [OKLA]	1,332,440	431,243 (32.36%)	2,370,980	749	695	647
<i>A. michauxii</i>	Fishbein 5614 [MISSA]	188,518	23,562 (12.50%)	56,291	128	120	11
<i>A. nivea</i>	Fishbein 6061 [OKLA]	368,108	44,594 (12.11%)	232,571	220	208	64
<i>A. notha</i>	Fishbein 5839 [OKLA]	470,458	32,275 (6.86%)	412,450	199	185	102
<i>A. nummularia</i>	Fishbein 6968 [OKLA]	329 532	26,165 (7.94%)	187 718	239	224	48
<i>A. nyctaginifolia*</i>	Baker 16385 [ARIZ]	1,722,362	698,870 (40.58%)	2,467,220	762	701	678
<i>A. oenotheroides*</i>	Bequaert 17 [US]	1,561,092	624,454 (40.00%)	2,395,271	766	703	690
<i>A. otarioides*</i>	Fishbein 5857 [OKLA]	1,740,686	270,968 (15.57%)	1,673,463	681	630	498
<i>A. perennis*</i>	Gust 706 [MO]	921,720	233,712 (25.36%)	161,7647	652	608	472
<i>A. pumila</i>	McPherson 765 [OKLA]	398,084	290,427 (72.96%)	3,217	14	13	3
<i>A. purpurascens</i>	Fishbein 6559 [OKLA]	377,070	1,737 (0.46%)	12,869	14	13	5
<i>A. quadrifolia*</i>	Fishbein 7488 [MO]	1,724,196	919,972 (53.36%)	2,804,470	763	703	695
<i>A. quinqueidentata*</i>	Fishbein 2850 [ARIZ]	1,460,018	243,161 (16.65%)	1,597,117	713	659	539
<i>A. rubra</i>	Fishbein 7210 [OKLA]	619 560	86,269 (13.92%)	673 831	400	372	192
<i>A. scaposa*</i>	Fishbein 7267 [OKLA]	2,725,774	1,266,475 (46.46%)	2,731,314	767	703	703
<i>A. schaffneri</i>	Fishbein 5846 [OKLA]	380,178	59,148 (15.56%)	305,746	353	326	76
<i>A. solanoana*</i>	Lynch 10884 [OKLA]	2,422,218	325,555 (13.44%)	1,113,289	719	661	469
<i>Asclepias</i> sp.	N/A	2 348 298	458,439 (19.52%)	79,629	271	249	27
<i>A. speciosa</i>	Fishbein 7521 [OKLA]	1 491 912	71,846 (4.82%)	537 320	277	256	150
<i>A. stenophylla*</i>	Fishbein 7509 [OKLA]	1,867,632	947,960 (50.75%)	2,851,285	763	703	693
<i>A. subaphylla</i>	Lynch 1008 [OKLA]	287,150	73,974 (25.76%)	16,624	67	65	4
<i>A. subulata*</i>	Fishbein 6446 [OKLA]	2,286,380	686,545 (30.03%)	2,560,580	763	701	686
<i>A. subverticillata</i>	Fishbein 2948 [OKLA]	514,124	187,685 (36.51%)	14,316	62	55	3
<i>A. syriaca*</i>	Data from Weitemier et al. (2019)	N/A	N/A	N/A	768	645	626
<i>A. tuberosa*</i>	Fishbein 7497 [OKLA]	1,987,916	1,014,026 (51.01%)	2,890,366	764	703	693
<i>A. variegata</i>	Fishbein 6764 [OKLA]	2 938 184	616,214 (20.97%)	2 260 339	266	266	156
<i>A. viridiflora</i>	Fishbein 7510 [OKLA]	1 070 296	15,161 (1.42%)	90 163	56	51	20
<i>A. viridis*</i>	Fishbein 7064 [OKLA]	451,438	150,702 (33.38%)	1,133,110	673	622	438
<i>A. virlettii*</i>	Fishbein 3005 [ARIZ]	2,489,766	570,898 (22.93%)	2,313,991	767	703	696
<i>A. fornicata*</i>	Chuba 276B [OKLA]	481,914	180,289 (37.41%)	1,271,372	697	647	467
<i>A. fruticosa</i>	Lambinon 95/493 [ARIZ]	1,192,486	13,887 (1.16%)	111,403	161	154	24
<i>A. physocarpa*</i>	Fishbein 6827 [OKLA]	3,153,950	1,508,647 (47.83%)	2,596,701	768	703	702
<i>Peryularia daemia</i>	Fishbein 6130 [OKLA]	890 834	368,411 (41.36%)	1 136 915	505	476	311

A.6 *ASTRAL* species trees for North American milkweeds (*Asclepias*)

Figure A4. *ASTRAL* species tree for North American milkweeds (*Asclepias*) with both PickMe suitable and unsuitable samples included. Unsuitable samples are indicated by an asterisk. Numbers near the nodes are local posterior probabilities.

A.7 Comparison with Individual Filtering Method

Table A2. Table comparing *PickMe* and Individual Filtering Method classifications of the *Iochroma* data from Gates et al. (2018). *Iochroma* samples as categorized by *PickMe* and Individual Filtering Method.

PickMe	Individual Filtering: Include	Individual Filtering: Exclude
exceptional	A_arborescens2428 A_arborescens250 A_arborescens98 E_fasciculata172 E_lorentzii184 E_lorentzii28 I_australe117 I_australe183 I_calycinum229 I_cornifolium231 I_cornifolium232 I_cornifolium249 I_cyan265_4 I_edule173 I_lehmanii_squamosum176 I_lehmanii228 I_loxense77 I_nitidum113 I_nitidum207 I_salpoanum181 I_tingoense112 I_umbellatum127 Nicotiana Physalis_peruvianum91 Potato Spimp Tomato	
very good	I_confertiflorum226 I_grandiflorum142 S_punctata178 S_punctata242	E_fasciculata133 I_baumii180 I_confertiflorum171 I_cyaneum170 I_ellipticum216 I_lehmanii150
good	D_obovata203 D_solanacea230 V_dichotoma177	D_brachyacantha208 D_solanacea185 D_spathulata136 D_spathulata141 D_spinosa114 I_cornifolium187 I_parviflorum132 I_parviflorum186 I_tupayachianum195 S_quitensis199 V_breviflora204
bad		
very bad		

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